

2-Chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone (2-Cl-QAT) as Analytical Reagent for Determination of Cobalt(II), Manganese(II) and Chromium(III)

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Manuscript received 17 August 1993, revised 11 January 1994, accepted 6 April 1994

Thiosemicarbazones have been frequently employed for spectrophotometric determination of inorganic ions¹. The present communication reports determination of Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} using 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone as the reagent.

Results and Discussion

The ligand is soluble in dimethyl formamide and water only and is stable for a week. The complexes of Co, Mn and Cr are also stable for 24 h. The complexes revealed characteristic ir bands at 3 120 (NH), 3 280 (NH₂), 1650 (C=C), 1 540 cm⁻¹ (=C-N). Electronic spectra in DMF and water mixtures at pH 6.5, 7.5, 9.5, showed λ_{\max} at 415, 375 and 360 nm respectively. The molar extinction coefficients of Co, Mn and Cr complexes were 0.175×10^4 , 0.117×10^4 and 0.127×10^4 respectively. The reagent was found to have $\lambda_{\max} = 480$ nm.

Determination of cobalt(II), manganese(II) and chromium(III) : Reaction of metal ion, the reagent (Cl-QAT) and buffer solution in DMP-water yielded the metal complexes. They are soluble in aqueous 20% (v/v) DMF solution. The reaction for the formation of complex is rapid and requires no heating for colour development. The characteristics of the complexes are summarised in Table 1. Dissociation constants were determined by the Job² and mole-ratio³ methods.

Tolerance limits of cations in determination of Co (2 ppm), Mn (2 ppm) and Cr (2 ppm) were determined. Tolerance limit of Co for Ga^{II} and Mo^{VI}

was 100 ppm. Tolerance limits of Mn were as follows : Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, Co^{II} (200 ppm each) and Pt^{IV} (20 ppm). Tolerance limits of Cr were as follows : Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cd^{II} (50 ppm each), Ni^{II}, Al^{III} (20 ppm each) and Mn^{II} (5 ppm). Tolerance limits for various anions (2% error) in determination of 2 ppm each of Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} were : cyanide, citrate, EDTA, nitrate, tartrate (each none), acetate, thiocyanate, oxalate, thiourea, phosphate, fluoride (each 1000 ppm).

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLEXES

Sl no	Characteristics	Co	Mn	Cr
1	Moles of reagent required per mol of metal ion	2	5	2
2	Beer's law range (ppm)	6	6	4
3	Optimum concentration range (ppm) (Ringbom plot)	1-3	3-7	3-5
4	Dissociation constant	7.960×10^{-6}	1.478×10^{-5}	1.088×10^{-4}
5	Mean absorbance	0.80	0.60	0.470

Experimental

2-Chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone⁴ was obtained by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide in minimum amount of ethanol for 1 h. The product was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 225–26°. Stock solutions (1 mg ml⁻¹) of metal ions were prepared. Following buffer solutions were prepared⁴ : pH 6.5, 7.5 and 9.5 for Co, Mn and Cr respectively.

The metal ion solution (containing 2.5–5.0 ppm metal) was mixed with $2.07 \times 10^4 M$ (2-Cl-QAT) and buffer (1 ml) and diluted to 10 ml with 1 : 1 DMF-water mixture. The absorbance was measured over region 350–650 nm against reagent blank. Maximum absorbance for Co was 415 nm while Mn and Cr had 375 and 360 nm respectively.

A Shimazu spectrophotometer was used to measure absorbance.

References

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